

From the series: The Grandeur of the Turkic World

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ABSTRACT: As known, in the ancient time the social and conceptual dimensions of Universe, Earth and of religion are expressed in the act of naming that is, cognitive creation human nature of ethnonyms and toponyms. And in the article the essence and value of concept 'Tengri-Gut', based on ancient Turkish beliefs in the uniform Tengri – Gut (or Gök Tengri) is investigated. In another hand, in the earliest period history of human rase theonyms has a been as crucial component of nomadic culture and all ancient social structure. As a result, not simple words were created, in other words, words 'clothed' with powerful connotations in the spiritual sense for a given language community, the so-called nuclear forms of ancient theonyms. Its study from the point of view of historical motivations and representations has been developed in the social sciences, in particular in cultural and linguistical geography. The author of article comes to conclusion, that Tengrianism as the religious system, originates from ancient representation about unity of the sky and the earth. Furthermore, the study of triadic-model 'theonym ↔ ethnonym ↔ toponym' presupposes the observation and analysis ancient theonyms from onomastic background and process, therefore focuses on phono-semantic inner interaction (sound interaction of words) triadic-model 'theonym ↔ ethnonym ↔ toponym'. Besides, within current issues and debates in the field of Geopolitical-linguistic scholarship, this paper is concerned with evolutions of natural human language and the semiotic construction of ancient onomastic elements. At the same time, of super-linguistic power from semantic internal form of ancient onomastic roots and present model as form nuclear triangle: 'lexeme ↔ toponym ↔ religion name (theonyms)' of modern global linguistics.

Key words: theonym, ethnonym, toponymy, etymology, areal geography, geo-linguistic areal, compound names, toponymical line low, appellative, agglutinative.

Introduction**Results and Discussion****Conclusion****References****1. Introduction**

According to scientists, approximately 10-12 million years ago powerful geological ruptures tore apart Asian Eastern plain leaving fissure running down the length of the continent the Great Fergana Valley formed by violent tectonic movements and volcanic eruptions it has created environments that a both hostile and beautiful in its Northeastern corner is the Asian continent that stands as a testament to this opposing forces. Middle and Central Asia is a land of extremes it's home mountainous Highlands, vast river valleys and arid deserts. And for each of this environment a different tribes can be found in its midst [1,28-29]. These ancient people are some of the world's most adaptable characters able to survive anything from nature. Indeed, Central Asia has a number of stanning mountain

ranges created by the collision of continental plates and huge volcanic activity we now have several major mountain ranges as Tian Shan, Tibet, Pamir, Ararat, Hindu Kush and Alay etc. Han Tengri largest of all in this region [3,403].

As we noted in previous studies [14,3387;4,403], the Altaic tribes an Ice Age Survivor and earliest Homo Sapiens settled on sunny plates Central Asia on earth chose Sun as God [4,403]. In time almost all elements of galaxy and nature became deities and totems of sun cults and were represented inhuman or fantastic forms. First all, Sun forming the basis of life on the Earth and organized religions that invoked the sun as the divine light of virtue.

Fig. No 1.

Thus, the theoretical linguistic conception illustrated by the anthropomorphic rock carving of the Sun God at Saimaly Tash in the Tien Shan mountains of Kirgizstan (4000-2000 B.C.). Bronze age spiral patterns are thought to have led to the earliest forms of hieroglyphic writing, the invention of the wheel, and the universally popular spiral design, as well as to the image of the halo as a sign of spiritual luminosity [4,388-407]. Proto Turkic society was introduced to the belief in the forces of nature, considered sacred. This consciousness is also the source of regulation of the Proto Turkic society, which lives in harmony with nature. The main advantage of this belief system was the perception of the universe as a whole.

A spectacle of stone, snow and light, in a time that seems to stand still. This is the Landscape of majestic mountain range Khan Tengri. For 12,000 years the Ancient Altaic people and their culture have occupied this sacred place on earth. These mountainous regions are up to 7,000 meters high and the Kyrgyz people call them Tengir Tow [Teñir Toō] 'mountain of Tengri'. They revere this severe region so it has been their home since time immemorial, a world-famous historical and linguistic mausoleum on the planet as well. They live in portable nomad house Bozuy [Boz új] that they weave themselves from sheep's wool and horse's hair. This is where the nomadic tribes who passed through this region thousand's years ago depicted their world themselves, of course, as hunters, but also the domesticated animals, without which life here would have been impossible [1,9-137]. Sometimes, they left behind for the next generation not just images but also verbal code and letters [14,3387-3396; 28,350].

Ancient Fergana Valley was created by a geological fault more than 11 million years ago. The earliest settlers of this region are the so-called Ancient Altaic tribes created distinct societies and built, a vast religion system galaxy religion names, or theonyms that cover continents in World. The significance of Gun, Tengri and Kut [36,749] as mad of clay, bronze and iconographic symbols is well known [4,213,216-217;41,242-243]. Considering the huge-amount of existing hypotheses and assumptions of scientists, we did of course try to analyze the etymological plan and diachronic evolution of these lexemes as efficient as possible.

Although, religion terms on ethnolinguistic vitality of Ancient Altaic languages in this region, has matured as a dynamic field of research. In the same time, we examine the linguistic factors of the areal Tian Shan, Tibet, Pamir, Ararat and Hindu Kush mountainous chains to understand historical-linguistic evolution Altaic tribes in this area, social, cultural, and ideological flows in globalization and hybridization. In addition, explore how different linguistic collectivities use cognates and semiotic resources in different geographical spaces to reinforce or contest existing ancient social structures, bearing strong implications for language maintenance and cultural revitalization, construction of ethnolinguistic and national identities, and geographical-linguistic mobility [26,23]. And looks into how globalization and its accompanying forces and influences, such as the importance of Western languages in socioeconomic mobility, into contact with local Asian cultures and firstly of ancient languages from Proto-Altay family [13,3387-3396]. In this sense pictograph Sun-God in Proto-Altaic Gun (< kynly 'children of Sun') become as old as writing itself and linguistic salience of languages on signs in Tian Shan, Tibet, Pamir, Ararat and Hindu Kush mountainous chains. Although, this ancient word Gun (< kynly) our ancestors became well known in scientific field and spread throughout Eurasian continent as it is mega-ethnonym Hun (< Gun) [13,3387-3396].

But language contact occurs always as the result of major population movements and mor of extralinguistic factors. Therefore, if we are to study the meaning of ancient cognates (particular of Ancient Altaic roots, e. g., Gün, Tenri and Kut) [36,749] and of linguistic interaction between local tribes, must also understand the historical, cultural and anthropological contacts which may be involved [26,615-619]. In the time, Attila's army traversed the ancient nomadic world, but the Ancient Altay and Oriental Iranian worlds did not clash. At the same time, Attila's conquest was followed by a slow and peaceful process of occidental to Ancient Oriental contacts [6,83-89]. In our case, partial infiltration of a new ethnic entity, while the old one, e. g. Ancient Iranian sedentary tribes, continues in residence in the same territory [9,67-71]. This, as we think, was the typical case during the epoch of ancient mankind. The local population, probably Ancient Iranians and Scythians, could either absorb the newcomers also linguistically, or it could adopt their language. Wherever, Soviet historians as V.Bartold [3,493-499], A.N.Bernstam [4,407-411] and B.G.Govurov told the presence of Turkic tribes on Han Tengri (Tian Shan, Tibet, Pamir and Hindu Kush mountainous chains) this time [12,225].

In a word, despite the unfounded hypotheses of our Western colleagues or rather scientists the main current theonyms as God, church, calendar, cell, alas etc. in modern European languages, 'unfortunately', are of ancient Turkic origin. Werther the or other event occurred, depends on strictly definable historical circumstances.

2. Results and Discussion

If we look at this issue more closely, the Earliest Homo Sapiens are linguistically emotional and self-conscious beings. Along with being physical and rational they have the capacity self-reflection almost ponder own nature as well. At the same time, the next step for understanding the world or/and universe of linguistic society of Ancient Altaic tribes happened with the creation of the God of the universe Tengri. Hence Tengri translated from ancient Turkic means 'creator' and according to the semantic formula acquires mutual linguistic nomination, as: 'Tengri ↔ Gud' [2,22-26]. The abundantly found ingots from Tengri are often found in archeological excavations in general, and ancient Turkic burial grounds (church < çəç) in particular. Gud//Kut can be found in worldview Ancient Altaic people similar to the code set out by believes these characters embody God of Tengri [36,749]. In ancient mythology Tengri slept at night at the summit of mountain Tomur (basis) (today mountain Pamir) and traveled during the day in the sky. When he gets angry, he calls deity of the thunder, thunderstorm and lightning - Gok [Ğöğ]. Therefore, the term Gok and Gok Turk appeared in religious terminology in historical studies.

On the other hand, the emergence of the religious concept of Tengri 'creator of the world' is formed among ancient Altaic tribes Verbal Code from doctrine of the eternal cycle of life on earth [12,260;2,22-26;27,212-222]. Ancient Altaic people therefore, according to the principle of concept from code of the eternal cycle of life, they chose the form of housing and universe-time concept or lunar calendar [8,202-210].

Fig. № 1

But continuous theory of natural human language process is not only strategies for scholastic facts storing easier, we also had to deal with questions of phono-semantic formation these ancient linguistic codes of the universe from the point of view of the nomads, who inhabited these majestic mountain ranges at dawn human history. Its first in-depth knowledge of ancient Altaic civilization directed and create a first Altaic calendar that predicted sola and lunar eclipses with more accuracy. Ancient Altaic people also introduced ancient civilizations to a new layout of the elements of celestial bodies.

In fact, Tengri is not an appellative or//and a common noun at all [36,1401-1402]. This connotative-sacred lexeme is the proper name of the creator of the universe Gök Tengri or the ancient form of the 'creator of the world' as well. Indeed, the use of this complex theonym by the Altai tribes for many thousands of years led to changes in the phonetic structure of this sacred nominative. But many scientists including linguists assume or think that Ancient Turkic Tengri means 'sky' [2,22-26; 14,3-4].

The question of inter-Altaic development may be observed in means of language contact during various stages according to the structure of inner development of Altaic family and particulars onomastic lexicon. Because, study of Ancient Altaic loans in neighboring linguistic areal (e.g., Ancient Iranian), borrowings in Common Turkic and glosses in non-Altaic languages (e. g., Celtic, Finno-Ugrians, Western part of Eurasian and Native American) shows different of Turkic languages in Eurasian continent since split of the Proto-Altaic language [39,100-102; 40,67-68].

However, according to Marcel Erdal: 'The fact that runiform alphabet was put to popular use in a vast area (including quite remote Siberian regions) coinciding with the roaming grounds of the early Turks, and not outside them, would equally speak for an original creation; the Tangut (< Tengri Gut – D.N.) and Qïtañ (< Gut Tengri – D.N.), e.g., have also invented their own writing systems. Although the runiform script is thus likely to have been devised by Turkic groups, the Türk empires which formed in Mongolia probably first used the Sogdian-Uygur alphabet, because they were introduced to sedentary civilization by the Sogdians' [22,11].

The Kyrgyz tribes are one of the ancient Turkic-speaking peoples who turned directly to classical Turkic literature and to the oral traditions of the Turks. These traditions, as a rule, are found in the written culture of the ancient Turkic people [26,64]. For example, the motive of venerating the sky as a deity runs like a golden thread through the Orkhon inscriptions. For example, let us turn to the monument in honor of Tonyukuk, where we read the following lines: 'The sky, perhaps, said so: I gave (you) a khan, you, leaving your khan, obeyed others. Because of this submission, heaven – one might think - struck (killed) (you). The Turkic people weakened and came down to nothing' [26,64]. However, in many languages of the Altaic family, of course, in the structure of the theonym Gök Tengri there were phonetic changes and semantic shifts occurred.

Fig. No 2. [36,1401-1402]

Because the main nominative load in these languages is carried out by the following component Tengri and means both: 'god' and 'sky'. For this reason, in the Turkic languages of the Siberian area, Mongolian, Manchu including Aini and Korean Tengri is used in the meanings of 'god' and 'sky' [36,1401-1402]. The emphasis on the celestial origin of the Turkic kagans is also found in the inscription, based on this, one must think that the sky, according to the ideas of the ancient Turks, acted as a divine power [26,64].

Further, the cognitive and semantic evolution of the theonym Tengri was accompanied by phonetic changes in the composition of this nominative, particularly to the initiatory consonant in the form 't → h → s ↔ ch' as well [42,1-3]. Example, forms of Ancient Turkic proper name of God [Teŋir] are on the whole fairly regularly constituted in many languages of the Altaic family. Also in this particular case, commonly known as Altaic hypothesis suggests common ancestry for several universally accepted language families spoken across Eurasia, namely the Turkic, Mongolic, Tungus, Korean and Japan families. For common origin in the basis lexicon of five families commonly known as Altaic. As insular as Japan seems to be, it has always been bound up in relationships with others Siberian languages, particularly with Ainu people on the Korean Peninsula and China [32,36-42;34, 297-329]. A complicated, but historically, also linguistically realistic, phonetic adaptation of a sacred theonym Gut through space and longtime could imply that an original deep-level genealogical relationship between Turkic, Mongolic, Tungus, Korean and Japanese may have later become overlapped and partially obscured by various contacts between the already separated branches, varying in intensity and continuance [44, 242-243]. Theonyms, although frequently derived from ancient cognates, elements of local common language ('Hun < Ğún; God < Ğūd//Ķūd; Calendar < Ğülendar' are good examples), constitute, a nuclear roots and cognates within a language, just as etymologies, place names and personal names do. In order to, languages evolve over space and time

much more ancient cognates pass through centuries. Illuminating the evolutionary history of theonyms is important because it provides a unique opportunity to shed light on the population history of the origin speakers. Example, one of the Altaic family, the Nivkhi language is isolate and is spoken by tribes inhabiting the lower reaches of the Amur River and the northern and central parts of Sakhalin in the Far East. The language has two main dialects: the Amur dialect and Sakhalin dialect. Both groups of native speakers are rather small: altogether about 2,000 to 4,000 people consider themselves Nivkh, and less than 3% of them are speakers of Nivkh language. For other dialects, it is extremely difficult to find native speakers, such as for the Poronaisk dialect and the Northern dialect. The most important is that, this language, thanks to its long-term isolation, has preserved the ancient form of Proto Turkic theonyms as Tengri (< ʦaŋruin) [9,232] and Gut [9,381]. Besides, more is of indigenous and cultural groups of coastal northeast Asia, as Evenk Tengri (< ʦaŋru) [9,23] and Gut (< Gyt) [9,265] including the Paleo Asiatic peoples (Yenisei tribes), and the Asiatic Eskimo [34,3-12]. Onomastic elements of linguistic variation among individuals often carry the religious and semantic memory of a speech community's ethnolinguistic past. Accumulating ancient cognates that languages evolve by a process of descent with modification 'theonym ↔ ethnonym ↔ toponym' and they form into distinct families in a manner similar to their speakers into different ethnic groups through diachronic history.

According to historians, the Proto-Altaic people further migrated towards the west and Pacific Ocean, and divided into two main streams, of which one flowed towards the Northern zone of Europe and Baltic area. This tribes reaches central parts of Northern Siberia, Far East and Alaska. Consequently, they advanced towards American Continental Land through the Bering Strait and by crossing over the Bering Strait they gradually spread out on large regions of both North and South America. For example, the Lakota name for the supreme reality is Wakan Tanka (<taŋkhr'ah), sometimes translated as Great Spirit or Great Mysterious, but literally meaning 'most sacred' [18,31].

There are still several important and very unexpected questions to be answered. Is curious, the words of Ancient Turkic origin gud//kut, gulandar and unjil are the etymon of the most relevant words or//and theonyms in both English and European languages: God, calendar and English (< unjilis) as well.

Indeed, onomastic boundaries are formed diachronically by the process of divergence, that is, by the gradual diversifications of an originally ancient nuclear roots into more distinct uniform. Ethno-onomastic diversification is often the result of expansion, for increasing geographical distance tends to favor onomastic diversity as well. Because, ethnolinguistic diversity without saying that mutual intelligibility, when viewed in the context of linguistic divergence, is a transitional phenomenon, for Altaic languages retain some degree of religion words.

In the beginning, the denotation of Proto Turkic word gud//kud was usually the ingots from Tengri [44, 242-243]. From a cognitive point of view, it is essential to note that theonyms and proper names exhibit prototype effects, that is, particular (groups of) names may show more or fewer of the phonetical and semantic features generally considered to typical names. Sometimes, these etymological meanings, however, are synchronically irrelevant as far as the description of a referent is concerned; and many cases, they are no

longer transparent. In fact, the function of direct referential identification is a characteristic that theonyms share with attributive components. For all nomads who inhabit Khan Tengri and Proto Turkic peoples, Tengri is considered as the highest cult of worship that does not have a specific time and space. In Proto Turkic beliefs, the world is the order established by Tengri (< Tanra), and everything that is in it was created by Tengri will. Belief in the sky (Gök), sun (Gun), moon (Ay), fare (ot) and earth (jer) and other existing beliefs, as in celestial religions, failed to cast a shadow on Gok Tengri as the only creative force. In another hand, Proto Turkic people believed that only the mountain ram Mural is closer to the space of Gok Tengri. That's why, at each small community or cooperative of nomadic families, the so-called Kutan//Koton acquired a sacred specimen-ingots of mountain ram Mural – Kut [44, 242-243]. In turn, these ingots of mountain ram Mural, depending on their geographical area, differed from each other in shape, color and material.

Fig. No 3.

Pazyryk's barrows. 5000 BC. [Marsadolov L.S. History of dating the Great Pazyryk's barrows (the developed directions and academic schools)// Antiquities of Siberia and Central Asia. No8 (20), Gorno-Altaysk, 2017. 108 p.]

In addition, in the Turkic mythological consciousness, there is a belief in the heavenly origin of the kagan, as well as in the 'gut//kut' sent down by the Turkic deity. Tengri, considered the creator of the universe, sent down the Gut not for the rise of the kagans and beks, but specifically for the rise of the Turkic nation. The belief in the heavenly origin of 'kut' also clarifies why the Hunnic kagan bears the title 'Kut Tengri' [Beydili, 2003, p. 206].

There are, of course, a study of the various of phonetic variants of the above mentioned theonyms (Gök, Tengri, Gud etc.) within the Turkic system and extralinguistic circumstances which is the most important source for object theory phonetic model-transition 'r → l', 'd → z → ʀ' or//and 'g → ʀ' in the Ancient Altaic languages [43,2-9]. The only ethnic marker and identity cord that can unambiguously be followed backwards in time is the sociolinguistic (onomastic) lineage, that is, the genetic (in the linguistic sense) identity of the language. This is the basic principle of comparative linguistics, and thanks to comparative work we have today a relatively comprehensive understanding of the language families of the world. Diachronically, each language family corresponds to one or more stages of past linguistic expansion, accompanied by capacity for changing [15, 198; 24, 3-9]. It is important to realize that linguistic continuity in time does not imply continuity in place. So, there are, we can follow any given onomastic lineage backwards in time to the corresponding protolanguage that can be reconstructed on the basis of the relevant

comparative onomastic evidence, we have in general information on the original location of the essential speech community of Turkic language family [9,247-250]. Recent progress in the dating methods of both archaeology and, in particular, human genetics, suggests that cultural features and genetic markers often exhibit a considerable local continuity. This continuity does not, however, extend to natural language evolution. Strong evidence from areal linguistic (dialect) parts of the world, such as Eurasian continent, suggests that languages are often changed where populations and cultures remain stable. Of all historical documents and factors relevant to ethnic identity, place names and ethnonyms is the least stable locally.

However, the linguistic status of verbal code 'theonym ↔ toponym ↔ ethnonym' as the two nominative-word classes that share central lexical-structural word building or linguistic vertical with formation paradigmatic elements. At the same time various common nouns (nominative elements) such as direct transition into geographical names and in on the various types of meaning that names may carry. So, when studying the history of 'theonym ↔ toponym ↔ ethnonym' formation and their structure, certain regularities are considered, such as conceptual-word meaning, the oldest use of cognates to this root and in connection with 'socio-different' adjectives (trade community). Consequently, the phonetic structure and meaning of Proto Altaic root's Gut, Calendar, Tengri and semantic variants is widespread in Eurasian continent because intensive interaction Turkic people with different the cattle-breeding people lived in a neighborhood with farmers [44, 242-243]. They interacting and interferences with each other (in the onomastic sense). The population size of a speech community and the size of the territory it occupies are also governed by cultural and political factors. Ultimately, it is historical chance that determines which speech community occupies any given physical region, that is, what language is spoken in that region. We may deduce this from populations in previously Eurasian areas of Iranian speech begin to show Tianshan-Tibetan influences coincidental with the appearance of Turkic peoples [20,198]. These, however, were important economically because of the lucrative salt trade and formed a significant substrate element in the shaping of steppe culture since it was the environment from which many of the Turkic tribes sprang from [20,12]. We shall be dealing with groups that were (and some still are) primarily pastoral nomads. That is, their fundamental economic activity was livestock production which was carried out through the purposeful seasonal movement of livestock and their human masters (living in portable dwellings call 'boz uj' in Kyrgyz language) over a series of already delineated pasturages in the course of a year. Therefore, this was not aimless wandering in search grass, as the cliché of the Chinese sources would have it. The ecology of given group's particular zone determined, to a considerable extent, the composition and size of its herds and the attendant human camping units calling in ancient Altaic noun kutan/hoton (usually 8-12 family units) [27, 212-225]. Certainly, as mentioned, ingots of Gut, were important because of the in everyday usage and formed a significant substrate element in the shaping of steppe culture since it was the environment from which many of the Turkic tribes independent for their hard nomadic life. During the same centuries the trail we'll follows the centuries as Old Salt Route between Ferghana Valley and Persepolis. Known as, another Old Salt Route between India and Persepolis began to circulate in Tibetan area sense ancient period history till today. Using non-linguistic evidence to narrow down the possible time and place for a common ancestral population also has value in

assessing potentially cognate vocabulary. While cognates stand or fall based on their sound correspondences, e. g., Gut//Kut, Gulandar//Calendar etc. not on non-linguistic data from parallel investigations of pre-history, it is useful to pay attention to cognates with potential linguistical or archaeological relevance. As, apart from such historical obscure cases, sometimes Tocharian's, particular 'salt-dealers' for the purposes deliver the product (salt), at the same time they carried this sacred theonym Gut and Calendar//Gulandar far beyond to the distinguish the Eurasian part was made rout to the other major states in Middle Asia included European continent. As already mentioned above it is exactly major population movements or/and migrations of Ancient Altaic tribes and nomadic peoples in a body over thousands and thousands of miles, that have been commonly assumed as the reason for the spread of Altaic linguistic families. Thus, began the long journey an ancient Altaic cognate-root Gut, Calendar and Injil the trade routes passed from the East to the West and connected the ancient civilization from Han Tengri through the ancient city an earth Gaznak, Jericho, Parphia to Roman Empire, and later on – Byzantium.

Most often, in effect expressed both by onomastic lexicon or non-verbal semiotic means, such as material culture. However, there is a lack of knowledge of interaction and substitutability of onomasticon and material culture in this process under various social, economic, and geographical circumstances. This conception will offer an over new ways of etymologizing Proto-Altaic names and ethnonyms and their interaction with in diachronic process as structural-semantic model: 'theonym ↔ ethnonym'. It will be shown that the traditional etymologies do not live up to today's standards of Indo-European linguistics (example, exacting only Indo-Iranian cognates in Eurasian continent). And our analysis shows in some cases the formerly one and only etymology is only one among several possible etymologies, in other cases some of the formerly offered etymologies can now be excluded and in other cases the conclusion must be that the theonyms, ethnonyms and nominatives came into being in another language or on another language-layer than formerly thought.

Fig. No5 [S. A. Starostin, A. V. Dybo, O. A. Mudrak An Etymological Dictionary of Altaic Languages//pp.155,749]

Ancient Turkic and in Kyrgyz languages both calling bozuy 'portable nomad house made of felt in a round shape according to the concept from code of the eternal cycle of life' (Fig. No 1.) and chronology (the calendar) un + jul respectively in Hebrew Injil Torah (Fig.

No 1.). According to the structural and internal law of all agglutinative languages in general, Turkic languages in particular, mentioned theonym has a temporary meaning as a prepositive component un in almost all Altaic languages 'is it whole or//and round' and subsequent part gul//jul 'year' [36,19-31]. By the way, there is no particular disagreement on this issue among linguists and scientists alike.

As for the word calendar in ancient Turkic gulandar, this ancient Turkic word had in its denotation as 'personnel obliged to deliver or//and convey information to the far corners of the mountain region'. And in this case, as we noted above, according to the structural law of the natural language (Ancient Turkic) of the ancient nomads the first component of the structure of this complex-nominative gul was an adapted variant of Ancient Turkic appellative ogul 'mature young man' and andar 'informer, carrier' as well [35,8]. Indeed, ethno-toponymical boundaries are formed diachronically by the process of divergence, that is, by the gradual diversification of an originally ethno-toponymic roots into more distinct uniform [33, 297–329].

There are many common Altaic roots which have no traces at all in the modern languages from Altaic family, whether standard or dialectal, but can be found still surviving in theonyms, place-names or ethnonyms. Fortunately, we can find a comprehensive selection of these meanings in several sources and Professor S.A.Starostin's volumes 'An Etymological Dictionary of Altaic Languages' co-authored with Anna V. Dybo and Oleg A. Mudrak [S.A.Starostin. Anna V. Dybo. Oleg A. Mudrak [An Etymological Dictionary of Altaic Languages, 3 volumes. Leiden: Brill, 2003, pp. 233, 398.1556 p.]. Also, this fundamental work significantly shows phonetical evolution and transformation ancient cognates kut 'cult of god' and gulandar 'calendar' to according Altaic model 'k → g' and non-Altaic languages with temporary umlaut consonants 't ↔ θ ↔ d' [41, 398, 399].

Fig. No4 [13,3387-3396]

Thus, linguistic history of Slavic languages shows different stages of evolution of non-Slavic loans e. g., God (< gud) 'god', calendar (< gulandar) and unjil (< unjül) from neighboring Altaic languages [49,436]. Indeed, after began the extremely fast expansion of the phonetic form these sacred verbal code as God [2,23-26; 28,347], calendar and annual across great parts of Europe as well.

3. Conclusion

However, the linguistic status of verbal code 'theonym ↔ toponym ↔ ethnonym' as the two nominative-word classes that share central lexical-structural word building or linguistic vertical with formation paradigmatic elements. At the same time various common nouns (nominative elements) such as direct transition into geographical names and in on the various types of meaning that names may carry. So, when studying the history of 'theonym ↔ toponym ↔ ethnonym' formation and their structure, certain regularities are considered, such as conceptual-word meaning, the oldest use of cognates to this root and in connection with 'socio-different' adjectives (trade community). Indeed, Hun Tengri region including Fergana Valley the cradle human civilization and preserving ancient place-names in this area now extremely important for investigation native language of the ancient civilization from this important geographical area in human history. As has been said above, from the point own view, mostly origin local system of sacred-names Hun Tengri and Fergana Walley derives from Ancient Turkic language. And our analysis shows the following strong linguistic and historical evidence:

- Proto-Turkic root Gut - (including some of phonetic variants) means as appellatives all of Proto-Altaic languages god and in onomastic field - in fact and its value cannot be overestimated as it is a key to the interpretation of the ancient theonyms Eurasian continent;

- Both ancient theonyms Gut//God (< Gut + ongor) and Calendar (< Gul + andar) and including Göğ Tengri reflects typological features as agglutinative characteristic Turkic language family and analytic stem composition of "noun + noun";

- Non, of them obtained inflectional typological characteristic of Indo-Iranian or/and Indo-European languages;

- Those complex names Gut//God (< Gut + ongor), Calendar (< Gul + andar) and Göğ Tengri also reflect diachronic process as structural-semantic model: 'proper-names ↔ theonym' and have a specific agglutinative Turkic ezafe word building pattern of "noun + attribute to prepositive noun".

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